

Brian Kaess Email Contact List of Friends, Family, Penpals & Genealogy Folks
by Brian Paul Kaess
(updated as of 2-14-2026)

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Nastaran, penpal from Mashhad, Iran. Ob-Gyn female.
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Benjamin Wiechoczek, 7C2R, great-great-grandson of Franz Michna and Johanna Krettek. Stated he built much of the Michna tree. Email: bjew.1.618@gmail.com
Gerd Herud, Researches Klementz side of family, Graz, Aurstria, g.herud@aon.at says he is FS# P7YK-6TZ (himself), b. 1945 in Vienna, Austria. His father is Walter Herud FS # LD11- N2K.
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Barbara Piasecka, res. of Norway, raise in Poland. contributor to Polish Origins. username Barb Oslo. She helped with docs on Drozdok's.
Arturro username for contributor at Genealodzy.pl helped clarify Buron marriage record problem along with Dirk Wendland of NRW, Germany, FS Contributor.

Wessal Al-Haj Ali penpal from Aleppo, Syria wessalalhajali622@gmail.com.

Nina Yakov penpal ninayak991@gmail.com from Gali, Abkhasia, Georgia, now Uckardes, Turkey.

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Linda De Benedictis (email: lindad406@hotmail.com) iscombing throughthe national archives and fold 3 for SAW records for cousins Stuart Gatewood Gibboney and Lewis Warfield Gibboney.

Xin Xin or Mandarin Chinese 欣欣, which usually means happy, joyful, and full of vitality, not the "信" (Xin) meaning "trust." Penpal world, Singapore/Phillipines, email: xinx8229@gmail.com